

International convergence of patent citations and the career length of patent examiners: An empirical study on triadic patents

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Abstract

Does a patent examiner rely more on external information sources for prior art searches as the examiner becomes more experienced? This question has importance in policy debate since studies confirm that the seniority of examiners leads to seemingly relaxed patent allowance in the US. This paper takes advantage of an empirical methodology to identify examination spillovers from the search result of the European Patent Office (EPO) to the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) in the sense that patent citations for rejecting a patent application tend to be “adopted” at a later office after the EPO issues search reports. This paper extends this approach to the Japan Patent Office (JPO) and analyzes how examiner seniority relates to the extent of receiving spillover at the USPTO and the JPO. Results show that more experienced examiners exhibit more convergence of patent citations at the USPTO and at the JPO with the search report outcome by the EPO, though the spillover effect depends also on international patent application routes of PCT or non-PCT.

Introduction

When an economically important invention is filed as an international family of patent applications in different jurisdictions, patent examiners across different patent offices start to examine the same technological content, simultaneously or sequentially. Wada (2018) showed that patent examiners at the trilateral offices of the EPO, the USPTO, and the JPO tend to cite different prior arts to reject applications in the same patent families even though the patentability criteria of novelty and inventive step (non-obviousness in the US) are close together. Wada (2020) then tracks examiner citations used for rejections (so-called “rejection citations”) across patent offices and has found that the same (international family of) patent citation is more likely to be employed at USPTO if a preceding search outcome by EPO is available for USPTO. Wada (2020) interprets the result in a way that there are spillovers from EPO to USPTO concerning the patent examination.

There are few prior empirical studies on how examiners in a patent office rely on prior citations generated by applicants and other offices (Cotropia et al., 2013). Based on the assumption of Wada (2020) that we can evaluate examination spillover via the convergence of rejection citations, we can assess if the same examination spillover exists other than in the EPO-USPTO relationship. Furthermore, utilizing the convergence of rejection citations as a trace of prior art search outcome spillover, this paper proposes to measure how the attributes of individual examiners, experience years in particular, are related to the susceptibility of inflow of search outcomes.

Among examiner attributes, examiner seniority has drawn much empirical attention because of its policy implications. Lemley and Sampat (2012) have found that more experienced examiners are more likely to allow a patent application at the very first office action. Many empirical studies followed, such as decreased time allocated to examine patent applications for newly promoted examiners led to lenient examination (Frakes and Wasserman, 2017). Its policy recommendation is to increase the time allocated for each examination because the scarcity of time limits the quality of patent examination. On the other hand, a recent study by deGrazia et al. (2021) scrutinizes the change of patent claims by amendments during patent

prosecution, and posits that more experienced examiners process patents more efficiently. As more allowance rates by senior examiners do not necessarily mean “leniency” of examiners, they suggest that more time allocation for examiners may not be necessary. Thus, the reason for the differences in allowance rates according to seniority is a key to inferring policy implications.

The question

Recent policy debates above highlight the need to establish more empirical findings on how seniority matters as a determinant of patent allowance rates. Does an examiner rely more on external information sources for prior art searches as the examiner becomes more senior? If so, it suggests yet another evidence for the scarcity of search resources being a determinant for examination quality, where “resources” could mean both time allowance per examination and the cognitive capability of examiners. To this end, this paper examines whether more experienced examiners exhibit more convergence of patent citations. Specifically, this paper tests whether an interaction effect of the seniority of an examiner and the change of citation convergence after EPO search reports become available.

In doing so, this paper compares two directions of examination spillovers from the EPO to the USPTO, and from the EPO to the JPO (we need to focus on unidirectional spillover from the EPO, not toward the EPO due to data limitation). Through the comparison, we will first be able to study if there are similar examination spillovers as a convergence of patent citations between EPO and JPO, just as it was observed between EPO and USPTO by Wada (2020). In addition, we obtain evidence on the differences of spillovers and seniority profiles as well. As will be summarized in the next section, examiners at the USPTO and the JPO have different profiles in terms of patent allowance rates along with their seniority. The examiners at the USPTO show a gradual and long increase in allowance rates along seniority, whereas the JPO examiners reach quasi-plateau earlier. By way of investigating citation behavior of the two offices, we may obtain clues about why senior examiners allow patents more, especially concerning information acquisition behavior.

Institutional background: patent allowance rates along examiners’ career

Do examiners at the USPTO and the JPO show a common tendency of increasing allowance rates as examiners become senior? Lemley and Sampat (2012) first established a finding at the USPTO, based on the rate of “first-action allowances,” which means patent grant decision at the very first office action for an application.

Figure 1 below shows a fractional-polynomial prediction plot of the probability of a patent grant at the first office action of USPTO, relative to the years of experience of examiners (the data sources will be explained in the next section). First-action allowance means a patent grant is given without any rejection. As is evident and consistent with prior studies (Lemley and Sampat, 2012), the first-action allowance is more likely, as the career of a US patent examiner is longer. Although somewhat concave, the increase is extensive until at least twenty years of their career. The plot shows a downward curve in the most senior range of examiners. However, the sample size of the most senior range is small, as is evident from Figure 2. Overall allowance rates along seniority seem to increase almost linearly for the majority of USPTO examiners.

Figure 1. Examiner experience in years and allowance rate at the first office action of USPTO. Fractional-polynomial prediction plot. N=84,487

Figure 2. Examiner experience in years and frequency of rejection actions, USPTO.

On the other hand, Figure 3 shows the same first-action allowance probability plot for JPO examiners. Like USPTO, it shows an increasing curve, though the increasing rate is much faster in the earlier half of their career. A contributing factor for the comparatively flat curve in the later halves of the careers is a flat workload along seniority. An interviewee (former JPO examiner) confirms that the expected number of cases processed in a month reaches a plateau within the first ten years of their career.

Figure 4 shows a histogram of examiner experiences, which exhibit an evident dip around 15 years of their career. This is due to the job rotation system at the JPO where examiners serve as patent judges in post-grant review procedures. They gain different perspectives as patent judges, which may result in a more efficient way of issuing rejection actions when they serve as examiners again. Another interview with a former JPO examiner confirms the curve, saying that at the very early stage of their career they often excessively try to avoid passage of filings, but that they learn to allow when they do not find a reason to reject. The level of passage does not monotonically increase throughout their career, according to the interviewee in Japan.

Figure 3. Examiner experience in years and grant rate at the first office action of JPO. Fractional-polynomial prediction plot. N=27,419

Figure 4. Examiner experience in years and frequency of rejection actions, JPO.

Methodology and data source

Conceptually, this paper adopts the same methodology as Wada (2020), which relies on rejection citations, namely, citations made by examiners to indicate specific prior arts to reject applications, as a key indicator across patent offices concerning an international family of patent applications. Examiner citations for refusals, which are assigned citation categories of “X” and “Y” at the EPO, JPO, and other offices, means the same for US rejection citations (sometimes called “blocking patents.”) At each patent office, examiners must indicate specific reasons to refuse patent claims, e.g., lack of novelty or inventive step. Because the standards of novelty and inventive steps are similar between the offices, the citation categories can be the common ground for comparisons of citations across offices. This can be augmented by the fact that cited patents can also be consolidated via international patent family data, though there is more than one patent family concept.

This study takes advantage of the same data set of US blocking patents used by Wada (2020), obtained from refusal documents (“CTNF” and “CTFR” documents) available as file wrappers on the “Public PAIR” database of USPTO, to compare patent citations employed by examiners specifically as reasons for refusals (Wada, 2018) at EPO and JPO. Namely, we measure convergence and divergence of individual refusal reasons used by the three patent offices through family-to-family citations. A similar US X/Y-equivalent database was developed independently by Jeff Kuhn (Kuhn et al. 2017), and yet another comprehensive database is made available by USPTO (Lu et al. 2017), which helped the idea of X/Y-equivalent citations disseminate. However, neither of them has a focus on international citations. We evaluate whether the availability of EP search reports has a positive effect on the rejection reasons at USPTO. Combined with the US blocking patent database, the EPO PATSTAT database (Spring 2016) is used.

The domain of statistical analyses is the set of triadic applications through PCT (Patent Cooperation Treaty) and non-PCT. Triadic patent applications are defined here as EPO’s DOCDB simple families (Martinez, 2011) that contain all of the EPO, the USPTO, and the JPO applications recorded on EPO’s PATSTAT database. Triadic applications are supposed to represent patent applications with high economic value. The domain of this study contains EPO DOCDB families where only a single DOCDB family ID is observed and where blocking patents are added by all of the trilateral offices, representing “twin applications.” The domain of the study comprises 274,100 family citations recorded as X/Y-equivalent at USPTO found for 40,577 citing triadic families with their priority year 2003-2010.

Several precautions should be mentioned in the data. First, all citation data are patent citations, because of the availability of DOCDB family-to-family citations. Thus, the accuracy of international families depends entirely on the DOCDB family table on PATSTAT. Also, because we could not consolidate the same non-patent literature across different records, we employ patent citations only.

Second, only the dates of search reports, not of post-report examinations, at the EPO, were reliably available for this study. Also, the EPO citation data during its examination phase is incomplete on DOCDB and PATSTAT. Therefore, we do not utilize examination timing information at the EPO. Search report dates for this study are combined, compared, and checked with the EPO DOCDB back file, and are confirmed accurate.

Third, triadic patent applications are defined here as DOCDB families that contain only one DOCDB citing family recorded in a family. Therefore, any divisional or continuation applications that produced more than one DOCDB family ID cause the family to be excluded from the sample.

Logit analysis

Methodology

To obtain micro-level insights, we employ the same methodology as Wada (2020) focused on the dichotomy of whether or not a US X/Y-equivalent is coded as an X/Y category at the EPO as well. By way of taking this dichotomy as a dependent variable in logit, we can analyze correlating factors and their signs. The unit of analysis is a family-to-family citation given at USPTO as X/Y-equivalent and JPO as X/Y. We run logit estimations on the full sample as well as on sub-sample of applications comprising of PCT and non-PCT. Let y be a binary dependent variable where $y = 1$ when a piece of rejection citation at the USPTO/ JPO is also recorded as X/Y at the EPO at the international family-to-family citation level, and $y = 0$

otherwise. Let X be the vector of explanatory variables x_j , and β_j be regression coefficients for x_j . Given x_j , we assume that the conditional probability of $y = 1$ is

$$P(y = 1 | X) = \frac{e^{g(X)}}{1 + e^{g(X)}} \quad \text{where } g(X) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \dots + \beta_p x_p$$

Explanatory variables and main predictions

The first set of key explanatory variables is dichotomy variables, *us_action_after_EP_SEA_date* (i.e., USPTO office action date after EPO Search Report date), and *JP_FA_later_than_EPO_A3A4* (i.e., JPO First office Action later than EPO A3 and A4 search reports). The value is one when a citation was given at USPTO/JPO by a rejection after the release of the EPO Search Report (ESR) for its European Patent family member application. Because of the “search result spillover” effect, we predict the coefficient to be positive. Note that we include all search reports issued by the EPO for the USPTO sample, which is consistent with Wada (2020). However, EPO A1 search reports are issued with the publication of a patent application, which is typically published after 18 months after its application. They are usually much earlier than A3 (separate search report) and A4 (supplementary search report). In order to compare the effect of the average timing difference between A1 and A3/A4, analyses will be given for the entire EPO-USPTO sample (A1/A3/A4 all included, model 1 below) as well as for EPO A3 and A4 only sample for USPTO (model 2-6 below). For JPO, the domain is limited to EPO A3 and A4 search reports only, because JPO first office actions in this sample were given much later than 18-month publication timings. Thus, the variable name for JPO ends with “A3A4” instead of “EP_SEA_date.”

The second set of key explanatory variables is the experience years of examiners, i.e., *US_examiner_experience_years* and *JP_examiner_experience_years*, respectively. They are defined between the beginning years of rejection documents with the same examiner ID and the timing of focal examination by the examiner ID.

The focal concern of this paper is whether an examiner relies more on external information sources for prior art search *as the examiner becomes more senior*. In order to test this, this paper tests whether an *interaction* term of the change of citation convergence after the availability of EPO search reports and the seniority of an examiner. In other words, these are products of the two focal variables explained above. Two interaction terms are thus defined as:

*US_examiner_experience_years *after_EPO_A3A4* for USPTO, and
*JP_examiner_experience_years *after_EPO_A3A4* for JPO.

Through the interaction terms, this paper examines whether more experienced examiners exhibit more convergence of patent citations.

Controls

We employ several control variables. First, the reasons for rejection can be distinguished in the USPTO sample. If prior art is found as a ground for novelty rejection, the piece of information can be easily shared among offices. Therefore, novelty rejection (*USC 102*) is expected to have a positive coefficient. On the contrary, inventive step (non-obviousness in the US) rejections are usually inferred through a combination of prior arts (typically Y-category citations), and are

more susceptible to examiner idiosyncrasy. Therefore, non-obviousness rejection (*USC103*) is expected to have a negative coefficient.

The location dummies for the priority country, *first_EP*, *first_US*, and *first_JP*, are employed. We also controlled priority years (2003-2010) and WIPO 35 technology fields of each family. A variable *techn_field_nr_counts* is the number of WIPO technology fields covered by the family, representing the breadth of technology. We also employ two dichotomy variables, *EP_applicant_cite* and *isr_cited_dummy*, concerning whether the citation pair is recorded as an applicant citation at the EPO and a citation from International Search Reports (ISR), respectively. If a citation is submitted by an applicant at the EPO, the applicant is likely to submit the same prior art to USPTO because of the duty of disclosure in the US. Therefore, citation coincidence between the two offices will increase for European applicant citations.

USPTO results

As the first row for the USPTO in Table 1 shows, EPO-USPTO family-to-family citation coincidence is consistently more likely after a release of its ESR. That is, we observe the convergence of citations after the release of ESRs in the US when all search report types (A1/A3/A4) are included (Model 1), and also when only A3 and A4 reports are included (Model 2-6). The results are consistent with Wada (2020). The estimated coefficient is less for PCT applications in Model 5 than in other models. As Wada (2020, p.1604) shows, USPTO first office actions are almost always issued before EPO search reports when PCT applications from the US obtain EPO A4 supplementary reports. These cases occur when US applicants choose the USPTO as their International Search Authority (ISA), which is as frequent as EPO as ISA. In those A4 cases, USPTO examiners do not have an access to EPO A4 reports before their first office actions. Therefore, the impact of this variable is seemingly smaller.

Concerning the focal interest of examiner seniority and citation convergence, more experienced examiners exhibit more convergence of patent citations at USPTO, which is shown in Model 1 and Model 2. Those are experience effects on the average. Most interestingly, US examiners show more convergence as a coefficient of interaction terms (*US_examiner_experience_years * after_EPO_A3A4*) in Model 3, 4, and 6. In those results, the coefficient of the simple US experience years has lost significance. It can be interpreted in a way that the convergence of EPO-USPTO citations is more pronounced among senior examiners because senior examiners adopt citations from EPO. In Model 5, no significant coefficients are found for seniority variables in the PCT sample. Although further scrutiny is needed, an interpretation can be given in a way that citation information supplied from EPO to USPTO in time for the first office actions at USPTO is limited compared to non-PCT applications, as is shown in Wada (2020). Also, unlike EPO and JPO, USPTO outsources International Search Reports for PCT applications, which may contribute to the observed lack of experience years effect in Model 5.

Table 1. Logit regression, dependent variable: coincidence dichotomy between rejection citation at the triadic offices of EPO and USPTO. Unit of analysis: DOCDB family citation pairs.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Sample range	Full, including cases with EPO A1 reports	Full	Full	Full	PCT	non-PCT
<i>us_action_after_EP_SEA_date</i>	0.477*** (0.0213)	0.323*** (0.0250)	0.243*** (0.0335)	0.249*** (0.0336)	0.131** (0.0433)	0.307*** (0.0554)

<i>US_examiner_experience_years</i>	0.00835*** (0.00131)	0.00649*** (0.00164)	0.00225 (0.00209)	-0.0000412 (0.00213)	-0.00176 (0.00253)	0.00580 (0.00401)
<i>US_examiner_experience_years * after_EPO_A3A4</i>			0.00963*** (0.00282)	0.00812** (0.00286)	0.00575 (0.00352)	0.0141** (0.00500)
<i>USC102</i>				0.286*** (0.0252)	0.237*** (0.0315)	0.357*** (0.0426)
<i>USC103</i>				-0.399*** (0.0320)	-0.396*** (0.0405)	-0.404*** (0.0521)
<i>EP_applicant_cite</i>	0.229*** (0.0273)	0.263*** (0.0365)	0.263*** (0.0365)	0.290*** (0.0367)	0.313*** (0.0497)	0.180** (0.0559)
<i>isr_cited_dummy</i>	1.137*** (0.0327)	0.862*** (0.0354)	0.862*** (0.0355)	0.862*** (0.0356)	0.967*** (0.0375)	
<i>us_action_lag_from_appyear</i>	-0.0156* (0.00744)	0.00310 (0.00951)	0.00244 (0.00951)	0.0158 (0.00950)	0.0523*** (0.0124)	0.0568** (0.0199)
<i>techn_field_nr_counts</i>	-0.0614 (0.0692)	-0.0288 (0.0836)	-0.0285 (0.0836)	-0.0238 (0.0834)	-0.0662 (0.106)	0.0952 (0.132)
<i>first_EP</i>	0.0119 (0.0405)	0.0438 (0.0618)	0.0440 (0.0617)	0.0529 (0.0618)	0.164 (0.0913)	-0.214* (0.0928)
<i>first_US</i>	-0.121** (0.0380)	-0.0541 (0.0458)	-0.0542 (0.0458)	-0.0595 (0.0458)	-0.0734 (0.0568)	-0.104 (0.0809)
<i>first_JP</i>	0.122*** (0.0342)	0.156*** (0.0413)	0.155*** (0.0414)	0.153*** (0.0414)	0.182*** (0.0510)	0.0707 (0.0724)
Constant	-1.696*** (0.0535)	-1.648*** (0.0651)	-1.610*** (0.0658)	-1.442*** (0.0742)	-1.504*** (0.0920)	-1.474*** (0.130)
Observations	102,719	70,247	70,247	70,247	46,720	23,527
Number of families	38,059	25,849	25,849	25,849	17,063	8,786

Robust standard errors in the parentheses, with clustering on citing families.

Significance level: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

35 WIPO technology field dummies and priority year dummies are included and controlled for citing families, though estimated coefficients are omitted for space reasons.

JPO results

As the first row for the JPO sample in Table 2 shows, EPO-JPO X/Y family-to-family citation coincidence is generally more likely after a release of European A3 and A4 search reports. That is, we observe the convergence of citations between EPO and JPO after the release of European search reports. Concerning the focal interest of examiner seniority, the interaction terms (*JP_examiner_experience_years * after_EPO_A3A4*) show positive and significant coefficients in the full sample as well as in the PCT sample. That is, more experienced examiners exhibit more convergence of patent citations at JPO as well as at USPTO after EPO's A3 and A4 reports are available, whereas senior examiners do not show higher convergence on the average (the coefficient of *JP_examiner_experience_years* does not show positive signs).

The effect is not significant for non-PCT applications reviewed at JPO in Model 4. A possible factor is the region of the priority, which is shown by a significant difference in the estimated coefficient for *first_JP* variable. Negative coefficients of this variable in all four models suggest that JPO examiners find different rejection reasons when the priority exists in Japan. They are knowledgeable in Japanese documents, and the documents are less frequently cited by EPO examiners. The non-PCT sample in Model 4 has a much larger coefficient for this variable in absolute terms, compared to other Models 1-3. Examination spillovers may be affected by the differentially advanced technologies in different regions, and therefore affected by the different languages of documents. Unlike the EPO-USPTO relationship where the English language is shared, language differences may be a factor especially for examining non-PCT applications at the JPO.

Overall, the results at JPO are similar to those of USPTO, in the sense that examination spillovers are observed both in EPO-USPTO and EPO-JPO. Also, as examiners become senior,

they tend to rely more on EPO's spillover, though the results are not observed in the PCT subsample of USPTO and the non-PCT subsample of JPO. The results of the combined samples are consistent with the understanding that seniority leads to more reliance on EPO.

Table 2. Logit regression, dependent variable: coincidence dichotomy between rejection citation at the triadic offices of EPO and JPO. Unit of analysis: DOCDB family citation pairs.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Sample range	Full	Full	PCT	non-PCT
<i>JP_FA_later_than_EPO_A3A4</i>	0.268*** (0.0232)	0.169*** (0.0434)	0.232*** (0.0525)	-0.0166 (0.0806)
<i>JP_examiner_experience_years</i>	-0.000104 (0.00136)	-0.00507* (0.00223)	-0.00365 (0.00257)	-0.00614 (0.00449)
<i>JP_examiner_experience_years * after_EPO_A3A4</i>		0.00766** (0.00281)	0.00755* (0.00335)	0.00598 (0.00529)
<i>EP_applicant_cite</i>	0.327*** (0.0324)	0.327*** (0.0324)	0.406*** (0.0426)	0.211*** (0.0514)
<i>isr_cited_dummy</i>	0.422*** (0.0292)	0.421*** (0.0292)	0.426*** (0.0340)	
<i>techn_field_nr_counts</i>	-0.0211 (0.0847)	-0.0221 (0.0846)	-0.0128 (0.0953)	0.0259 (0.164)
<i>first_US</i>	0.103** (0.0396)	0.100* (0.0396)	0.132** (0.0473)	0.0572 (0.0737)
<i>first_JP</i>	-0.249*** (0.0392)	-0.251*** (0.0392)	-0.141** (0.0493)	-0.468*** (0.0674)
Constant	-1.646*** (0.0551)	-1.579*** (0.0601)	-1.686*** (0.0728)	-1.278*** (0.109)
Observations	132,221	132,221	90,084	42,137
Number of families	27,146	27,146	17,850	9,296

Robust standard errors in the parentheses, with clustering on citing families.

Significance level: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

35 WIPO technology field dummies and priority year dummies are included and controlled for citing families, though estimated results (including those for constant terms) are omitted for space reasons.

Discussion and conclusion

In a summary, we generally find EPO-USPTO as well as EPO-JPO convergence of citations after ESR releases, implying examination spillover from the EPO to the USPTO as well as the EPO to the JPO. However, we find variations of this spillover effect according to subsamples by international patent application routes of PCT or non-PCT. The relative timing of different office actions at the trilateral offices varies by international application routes, which needs further research.

We find that more experienced examiners generally exhibit more convergence of patent citations at USPTO and also at JPO in a less pronounced way. The difference between the two offices exists in the average convergence rate. The tendency for more convergence by more experienced examiners is similar, where convergence is observed. Namely, we have found that the longer the career length of examiners become, the more likely they become to cite the same prior art with EPO if they can observe search outcomes by the EPO. This result is consistent with the different patent allowance rates along examiners' career lengths at the two offices. Since citations for rejecting the same international family of applications reveal how examiners perceive prior arts, this study adds a clue to the policy issue concerning why experienced examiners are more likely to allow a patent.

The difference in the curve at the two offices of USPTO and JPO does not seem to play many roles. As examiner seniority increases, the level of allowance also increases throughout their career at both offices, which can be attributable to more reliance on external sources of prior art information, including EPO.

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